

FRIETS: Predicting Fungal Contamination and Mycotoxin Risks in Soft Fruits

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Fungal spoilage in soft fruits like strawberries, raspberries, and blueberries poses economic risks to growers and distributors, along with the potential for mycotoxin contamination, threatening food safety. The FRIETS* project aims to develop processed soft fruits with improved quality, nutrition, and shelf-life, while also addressing fungal contamination and mycotoxin production risks. The project focuses on creating risk and prediction models for fungal growth and mycotoxin production at different stages of the soft fruit production chain, including post-harvest handling and storage. By analysing environmental factors, cultivation practices, and storage conditions, the project aims to identify key influencers of mycotoxin contamination and establish guidelines for control. The project also assessed prevalent fungal strains, mycotoxins, and derivatives to construct a comparative risk assessment system, facilitating the prioritization of fungal and mycotoxin hazards in soft fruits. Using statistical methods like rank order correlation, we aimed to manage uncertainty and variability, enabling tailored risk mitigation strategies. Ultimately, seeking to enhance food safety and quality assurance in the soft fruit industry, fostering consumer confidence and promoting sustainability. Through advanced research and technology, the project aims to strengthen the supply chain against fungal contamination.

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